

THE ROLE OF TRANSLATION THEORY IN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATION IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract: The article studies the role of translation theory on implementation of interlingual communication in the learning process. The views of scientists about the model of translation as a means of interlingual communication were analyzed. Examples on how multilingual peoples perceive, interpret and describe various situations and situations occurring in the world, based on their own worldview, are given.

Key words: act, function, communication, linguistics, verbal, nonverbal, paraverbal, translation, Otto Kade.

Introduction. It is known that the main form of human activity is communication. A person becomes a conscious being, constantly striving to enter into communication. But before creating a model of communication in translation, it is desirable, in general, to make an act of speech, that is, a model of monolingual communication.

The main function of the language is a phrase that helps to communicate. Communication, that is, interaction, is a socially binding process of information transfer and information exchange. Cases from social life are reflected in the daily communication of participants in social communication, that is, in colloquial speech, in emotional isolation, in business communication. Figurative expressions used in speech indicate the continuity of people, the level of national mentality, thinking and the relationship between them.

A scientific study of foreign specialists in the field of modern linguistics has shown that the nature, form and style of communicative interaction, the first minute of communication are sometimes known in seconds. Therefore, in the field of communications, there are types of applications that can mitigate any situation. For example, calling the name of the interlocutor with a smile on his face guarantees that the conversation will continue in a friendly tone. [2, p.65].

When we say "communication", we understand the information transmitted from one participant of communication (source, author, sender of information) to the second participant (recipient of information, addressee, receptor). The source of information can be in oral or written form; the reception of

information can be carried out both in auditory (hearing) and visual (reading, vision) forms [2, p. 84].

The source code is used to transmit information, that is, the language of communication. The communicative behavior of the source is formed through the text (oral or written). Of course, in this regard, the communication of the intruders is not carried out when the connection is disconnected from the outside world. Therefore, communication takes place in different ways and in different situations with different influencing factors of the outside world.

As for the types of communication, they are usually divided into three types: verbal (that is, through words), nonverbal (behavior, facial expressions, body movements), paraverbal (intonation, timbre of sound, speed of speech, etc.).

It is known that the model of translation as a means of language communication was developed by the famous translator Otto Kade. [1, p.21]. Only in this model is the process of transcoding between the primary and secondary states introduced, the interpreter receives information encoded in one language and sends it back to the receptor of the second language by transcoding.

The result of the analysis shows that translation is not only a means of communication between two languages, but also a means of communication between cultures. A text created in one cultural environment may be misinterpreted or not understood at all in a second cultural environment. At this point, it is necessary to mention again the hints about the predicate situation. People of different languages perceive, interpret and describe different situations and situations that occur in the world based on their outlook.

For example, to depict terraces on the sea in Russian, it is said that the terraces fall to the sea. And English-speaking peoples say that the same landscape rises above the sea. Another example is when Russian-speaking peoples perceive the rise and fall of the sea horizontally, that is, "отлив и прилив моря", Farang-speaking peoples describe the rise and fall of the sea (marée haute - marée basse). In another example, sour cream on milk is described by Russian-speaking peoples in the style of "пенка на молоке", and by English-speaking peoples in the style of "milk with skin on it".

Conclusion. Of course, in order to convey these subtleties to the reader in this place, the translator's translation skills will be great. Translating a text related to one culture into another while preserving the purpose, content and character of the original text requires great skill, a high level of knowledge, a broad outlook, deep knowledge and skills from the translator.

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